

Title of the work:
Burning Thoughts.

Contributing artist:
Jaime Lobato.

Clear description of the proposed installation:

This sculpture addresses the topic of diverse artifacts that men created throughout history to conjure up nature. —Amulets, rituals, words, etcetera— It intends to include the Electroencephalography (EEG) in this tradition. For that purpose, it was intended to create a magic ritual where the public can materialize their brain activity through fire modeling in real time and see themselves reflected in it. An interactive mirror than can be, not only seen, but heard and felt is created. During this act of techno-shamanism, the public will also control their brain activity at will by trying to repeat a gesture made by the self-portrait of fire.

Technical rider

- 1 eeg sensor.*
 - 1 computer (MACOS or Windows).*
 - 1 Audio amplifier.*
 - 1 gas tank.*
 - 1 Ruben's tube.*
 - 2 pedestals, one 110x35x60 cm for the sculpture, and another 30x30x60 cm for the sensor.
(The measures can change a little)
- *provided by the artist.

Space requirements:

This installation needs a closed space than can be ventilated easily, is impossible to have it outdoors.

Images and videos:

<https://www.jaimelobato.com/en/work/sculpture/burning-thoughts/>

BurningThoughts

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Section Plan

- Audio Connection
- Gas Supply
- Electrical Outlet

Burning Thoughts

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Floor Plan

